

Exchange Rate Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around exchange rate risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 1979 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Exchange Rate Risk". Based on the search results, there were 239 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to exchange Rate risk is divided into 11 clusters and 118 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 6 main themes related to exchange rate risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Exchange Rate Risk, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Sharia and Conventional Banking

INTRODUCTION

Risk management in banking has improved in line with developments in the financial industry as a whole. In recent years, banks have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate risk exposure management and effective corporate governance. Risks in the financial sector must be recognized and controlled by estimating the potential that may occur in the future, not after the risk has already occurred. Therefore, a methodology for modeling risks that may occur in the future is very important so that those making decisions can prepare strategies to overcome future risks. One of the risks that occurs in the financial industry is exchange rate risk. Exchange rate risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, the development of exchange rate risk in banking is one of the risks that must be considered. In banking, exchange rate risk can develop due to various factors such as fluctuations in foreign exchange rates, changes in interest rates, monetary policy, global political and economic instability. Exchange rate risk can occur due to changes in the value of foreign currency against domestic currency. Banks that conduct international business and conduct operations in foreign currencies are at risk of being affected by changes in exchange rates. Therefore, banks must have good risk management to overcome unexpected changes in exchange rates. In recent years, developments in technology and global financial markets have also influenced exchange rate risk in banking. For example, developments in technology provide faster and cheaper access to conducting currency transactions and monitoring markets. This allows banks to more quickly and efficiently manage exchange rate risks. However, increasing interconnection and the need for global liquidity also increase exchange rate risk, so banks must continuously monitor and evaluate exchange rate risk and take necessary actions to minimize the negative impact of currency fluctuations. So, banks must continue to improve exchange rate risk management to ensure the stability and continuity of their business.

Based on the problems above, it is necessary to map exchange rate risk management topics to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around exchange rate risks

in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Exchange rate risk is the risk that arises from fluctuations in currency exchange rates. In the banking business, banks often carry out transactions in foreign currency, such as accepting deposits in foreign currency or borrowing in foreign currency. Fluctuations in currency exchange rates can affect the value of bank assets and liabilities denominated in foreign currency, thereby affecting bank profitability. If, for example, a bank has loans in foreign currency and the value of the foreign currency falls against the domestic currency, then the cost of borrowing in the domestic currency will increase, reducing the bank's profitability. Vice versa, if the value of foreign currency increases against the domestic currency, then bank profits in domestic currency will decrease. Therefore, exchange rate risk in banking is one of the risks that must be taken into account and managed well by banks. Banks can manage this risk by hedging by buying or selling derivative contracts such as forwards, futures or options. However, hedging also has its own risks that must be taken into account and managed properly.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature. Some applications of bibliometric studies include citation network analysis, cluster analysis, and visibility analysis. Results from bibliometric studies can be used by researchers, government, and industry to understand developments and contributions in scientific fields and to determine future research directions.

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

Studies Literature review is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions. Literature review studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment and produce non-duplicative results. It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Literature review studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Literature review studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object

of the research is exchange rate risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on exchange rate risks in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Exchange Rate Risk " within the entire year period (1979 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Exchange Rate Risk in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 239 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1979 to 2022. There are 39 journals Scopus indexed international. And there is 200 international and national journals indexed by Sinta around exchange rate risk research.

Journal publication data regarding Exchange Rate Risk by year							
Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1979-1999	33	2005	6	2011	4	2017	19
2000	4	2006	1	2012	11	2018	14
2001	5	2007	5	2013	7	2019	24
2002	8	2008	2	2014	7	2020	19
2003	2	2009	2	2015	10	2021	14
2004	5	2010	7	2016	10	2022	20

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Exchange Rate Risk in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are several things that need to be considered when knowing bibliometric results with software VOSviewer, namely: first, the software interface, namely the VOSviewer interface displays diagrams and graphs that visualize publication data. Users can open and explore these charts and graphs by clicking on specific items or zooming in on specific parts of the diagram. Second, visual components, namely several visual components that may appear in VOSviewer bibliometric results including nodes (representations of publications), lines (representations of citation relationships), and colors (representations of categories or topics). Third, citation network analysis, namely citation network analysis helps in determining relationships between publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Larger nodes in the diagram represent more widely noted publications and relationships between nodes can help in understanding how publications are related. Fourth, cluster analysis, namely cluster analysis helps in determining relationships between topics or fields of science and understanding how

- Cluster 6, consists of 10 topic items, namely: bank size, banking risk, banking sector listed, capital adequacy, car, covid, financial performance, profit, shadow banking, significant effect.
- Cluster 7, consists of 8 topic items, namely: bank profitability, bei, commercial bank, credit, efficiency, Ghana stock exchange, Indonesia stock exchange, credit risk problems.
- Cluster 8, consists of 8 topic items, namely: Amman stock exchange, bank risk, banking industry, Dhaka stock exchange, exchange risk, investment, profitability, Warsaw stock exchange.
- Cluster 9, consists of 7 topic items, namely: banking supervision, credit risk, financial statements, foreign exchange transactions, IDX, interest rate risk, operational risk.
- Cluster 10, consists of 5 topic items, namely: assets, exchange rate risk, management, portfolio model, Turkish banking sector.
- Cluster 11, consists of 1 topic item, namely: capital adequacy ratio.

Mapping Literature Review around the Definition and Objectives of Exchange Rate Risk Management

First, the definition of Exchange Rate Risk, viz risks arising from changes in foreign currency exchange rates which affect the bank's financial position. In the world of banking, banks often carry out transactions in foreign currency such as loans, investments and other operational activities. Therefore, changes in foreign exchange rates can affect a bank's profits and its financial exposure. FX risk can be grouped into two types, namely transaction risk and book value risk. Transaction risk is the risk that arises from changes in foreign currency exchange rates when carrying out transactions, such as buying or selling foreign currency. Book value risk is the risk arising from changes in foreign currency exchange rates on a bank's financial position, such as loans or investments in foreign currencies. To overcome FX risk, banks can hedge using financial instruments such as options, futures or forwards. contracts. However, hedging also has its own risks, so banks must carefully consider the advantages and disadvantages of each hedging strategy used.

Second, the aim of Exchange Rate Risk management is to ensure the stability and continuity of the banking business, as well as to reduce or eliminate the negative impact of changes in exchange rates on the financial position and performance of banking. Some of the main objectives of exchange rate risk management in banking include: (1) One of the main objectives of exchange rate risk management is to minimize potential losses caused by changes in exchange rates; (2) By reducing exchange rate risk, banks can increase profitability and optimize their financial position; (3) Exchange rate risk management ensures that changes in exchange rates do not significantly affect the stability of the banking business; (4) Exchange rate risk management helps banks to manage and understand exchange rate risks related to their business activities; and (5) Banking reputation is very important and exchange rate risk management helps to ensure that banking is not negatively affected by changes in exchange rates.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Exchange Rate Risk Monitoring

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Commissioners include: (1) Ensuring that banking management understands and manages exchange rate risk well; (2) Ensure that banks have the necessary resources to manage exchange rate risks, including appropriate personnel and technology; (3) Ensure that banks have procedures and systems to regularly monitor and evaluate exchange rate risk performance; (4) ensure that banks have adequate levels of control and transparency in managing exchange rate risks; and (5) ensuring that banks have effective mechanisms for reporting and communicating exchange rate risks to shareholders and other interested parties.

Second, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Directors include: (1) Determining and supervising the implementation of exchange rate risk management policies and

strategies, including risk limitation, risk measurement and risk control; (2) Ensure that banks have adequate systems and procedures to identify, assess and manage exchange rate risks; (3) Ensure that banks have adequate human and technological resources to manage exchange rate risk; (4) Approve periodic reports on the situation and results of exchange rate risk management, including important issues and actions taken to address risks; and (5) Provide direction and suggestions to management regarding efforts that can be made to manage and limit exchange rate risk.

Third, related to Human Resources/HR in banking, it plays an important role in managing exchange rate risk. Some ways in which HR can help in overcoming exchange rate risks include: (1) Appropriate training and education can ensure that bank employees understand exchange rate risks and how to manage these risks; (2) Human resources who have experience and expertise in risk management can assist banks in monitoring and managing exchange rate risks effectively; (3) Bank employees who are competent in risk assessment and monitoring can assist banks in monitoring market trends and making appropriate decisions to manage exchange rate risk; and (4) Human resources who understand technology and have expertise in developing technological systems can help banks manage exchange rate risks more efficiently and effectively.

Fourth, it relates to the Exchange Rate Risk Management Organization. The Exchange Rate Risk Management (FX Risk Management) organization in banking aims to monitor and manage risks associated with changes in currency exchange rates. This risk can arise because banks conduct business in various countries and handle transactions in various currencies. The exchange rate risk management process includes risk identification, risk evaluation, developing strategies to manage risks, strategy implementation and risk monitoring. The main objective of this process is to ensure the financial stability of banks and minimize losses that may arise from exchange rate fluctuations. To manage exchange rate risk, banks can use various instruments such as hedging, diversification and hedging. Hedging is the process of limiting or eliminating risk by placing an offsetting position in another market. Diversification is the process of expanding an investment portfolio to reduce risk. Hedging is the process of limiting potential losses by limiting the maximum amount that can be lost on any position. Exchange rate risk management is very important for banks because exchange rate fluctuations can affect banking financial stability and cause significant losses. Therefore, banks must ensure that they have an effective risk management system and carry out risk management processes consistently and regularly.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Strategy, Risk Level, Policies, Procedures and Limits in Exchange Rate Risk Management

First, the Exchange Rate Risk management strategy. Exchange rate risk management in banking is very important because currency fluctuations can affect banking profits and liquidity. Several exchange rate risk management strategies in banking include: (1) Hedging with financial instruments such as forward contracts, futures contracts and options contracts; (2) Diversify assets and liabilities by opening accounts and borrowing in different currencies; (3) Use of risk management tools such as limit orders and stop-loss orders to limit losses; (4) Increasing transparency and discipline in the risk control process; (5) Maintaining sufficient liquidity to meet needs that may arise from changes in exchange rates; (6) Establish an effective risk monitoring and control system; and (7) Involve professionals who understand exchange rate risk in the decision-making process.

Second, the level of risk to be taken (Risk Appetite) and risk tolerance (Risk Tolerance) on Exchange Rate Risk. Risk appetite and risk tolerance are two important concepts in managing exchange rate risk in banking. Risk Appetite is the amount of risk that a company or institution can accept. In this case, banks can have different levels of risk for exchange rate risk, depending on their objectives and business strategy. For example, a bank that focuses on international business may have a higher level of exposure to exchange rate risk than a bank that focuses on the domestic market. Risk Tolerance is the maximum risk limit that can be accepted by a company or institution in achieving its goals. In this case, banks may have different maximum risk limits for exchange rate risk, depending on their financial capacity and the level of risk they can accept. For example, a bank that has strong financial levels and has a high level of risk tolerance may be

better prepared to take higher exchange rate risks than a bank that has weak financial levels and has a low level of risk tolerance.

Third, the Exchange Rate Risk policy, namely a series of steps taken by banks to manage and reduce risks associated with currency exchange rate fluctuations. Exchange rate risk can arise because banks hold or trade assets and liabilities denominated in different currencies. Exchange rate fluctuations can affect the value of bank assets and liabilities, and therefore, affect business continuity and bank performance. Several policies that can be taken by banks to manage exchange rate risk include: (1) Hedging, namely banks can hedge using instruments such as forward contracts, currency swaps, or currency options to limit their exposure to exchange rate risk; (2) Diversification, i.e. banks can expand their business to countries with different currencies to reduce the risks associated with fluctuations in the exchange rate of one particular currency; (3) Limiting exposure, namely banks can limit the amount of assets and liabilities in certain currencies to reduce risks associated with exchange rate fluctuations; and (4) Risk monitoring and control, namely banks must monitor and control exchange rate risks regularly, update their risk management plans in accordance with market changes and ensure that they have sufficient resources to manage these risks. Exchange rate risk policies in banking are important to ensure that banks can manage the risks associated with exchange rate fluctuations and maintain their financial stability. However, this policy must be implemented carefully so as not to negatively affect bank performance.

Fourth, the Exchange Rate Risk procedure. includes the following steps: (1) Risk identification, namely the bank must identify sources of exchange rate risk, which may include foreign currency positions, foreign currency transactions, and credit exposure to foreign currencies; (2) Risk analysis, namely banks must carry out exchange rate risk analysis by estimating potential losses that may occur as a result of currency fluctuations; (3) Risk assessment, namely the bank must consider the potential impact of exchange rate risk on its financial position and consider alternative risk management strategies; (4) Planning risk management strategies, namely banks must determine appropriate risk management strategies for their situation, for example by using derivative contracts such as currency options or currency swaps; and (5) Strategy implementation, namely after a risk management strategy has been established, the bank must ensure that the strategy is implemented appropriately and that all foreign currency transactions comply with applicable financial and regulatory requirements; and (6) Monitoring and evaluation, namely banks must monitor and evaluate exchange rate risk management strategies periodically to ensure that these strategies function well and ensure that risks remain within acceptable limits.

Fifth, the Exchange Rate Risk limit, namely the limit applied by banks to control and limit potential losses that may occur due to fluctuations in currency exchange rates. Banks generally have an exchange rate risk limit for every transaction they carry out in foreign currency, with the aim of ensuring that possible losses do not exceed certain limits. Exchange rate risk limits can be applied to various types of transactions, such as buying and selling foreign currencies, funding in foreign currencies, and derivative transactions such as forward contracts and foreign exchange options. Banks can also use hedging tools such as forward rate agreements (FRAs) and options to limit exchange rate risk. By limiting exchange rate risk, banks can minimize potential losses that may occur and ensure that their exposure to exchange rate risk remains within acceptable limits. However, exchange rate risk limits can also affect a bank's ability to take advantage of opportunities that may arise as a result of changes in exchange rates. Therefore, banks should consider carefully whether the exchange rate risk limits they set are the best for their business.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Identification, Monitoring, Control and Exchange Rate Risk Information Systems

First, identify Exchange Rate Risk, there are several things that need to be considered, such as: (1) Banks must identify their exposure to foreign currency, such as loans and deposits received or given in foreign currency; (2) Banks should consider currency volatility and how this

may affect their exposure; (3) Banks must monitor central bank policies in terms of currency devaluation or revaluation; (4) Banks must take into account how international trade can affect currency exchange rate fluctuations; and (5) Banks must monitor market conditions and how these may affect currency exchange rates.

Second, monitoring Exchange Rate Risk is an important thing to do to ensure banking financial stability and minimize losses that may occur due to exchange rate fluctuations. There are several ways that can be used to monitor exchange rate risk, including: (1) Banks must identify sources of exchange rate risk that may arise in their business, such as foreign currency transactions, overseas investments, and others; (2) Banks must conduct exchange rate risk analysis to assess the level of risk that may arise from each source of risk; (3) Banks must determine acceptable exchange rate risk limits and ensure that business activities do not exceed these limits; (4) Banks must ensure that exchange rate risk management is implemented correctly and carried out regularly; and (5) Banks must continue to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of their exchange rate risk management and make changes if necessary.

Third, controlling Exchange Rate Risk, is an effort to minimize potential losses arising from changes in currency exchange rates. Exchange rate risk can arise due to banking activities such as offers and purchases of foreign currency, financing in foreign currency, and others. The following are several ways that can be done to control exchange rate risk in banking:

- (1) Hedging, namely the action of limiting risk by opening a position that is opposite to an existing position. For example, banks can open short positions in currencies that are expected to weaken, thereby limiting potential losses that may occur.
- (2) Diversification, namely the action of dividing risk by spreading positions into several different currencies. For example, banks can open positions in several currencies that have different levels of volatility, thereby limiting the risks arising from changes in the exchange rates of certain currencies.
- (3) Position limitation, namely the action of limiting the number of positions opened in a particular currency. For example, banks can set position limits on currencies that have a high level of risk, thereby limiting potential losses arising from changes in the exchange rates of these currencies.
- (4) Monitoring and monitoring, namely actions to continuously monitor changes in currency exchange rates and take appropriate action if necessary. For example, banks can monitor changes in currency exchange rates and open short positions in currencies that are expected to weaken, thereby limiting potential losses that may occur.

Fourth, the Exchange Rate Risk Management Information System (Foreign Exchange Risk Management Information System), which is the system used by banks to manage exchange rate risk. This system helps banks identify, assess and manage risks associated with changes in foreign exchange rates. This system consists of several components, including a risk identification module, a risk evaluation module, a risk control module, and a monitoring and reporting module. The risk identification module helps banks identify sources of exchange rate risk, such as foreign currency trading activities or investments abroad. The risk evaluation module helps banks assess the level of risk and estimate potential losses that may occur. The risk control module helps banks determine strategies to address risks, such as limiting foreign currency trading activities or hedging through financial instruments such as currency options. The Exchange Rate Risk Management Information System also provides reports that monitor risk developments and help banks assess the effectiveness of the risk control strategies used. Thus, this system helps banks ensure that exchange rate risks can be managed effectively and that the bank's financial position remains stable.

Fifth, the Exchange Rate Risk Internal Control System (Foreign Exchange Risk Management System) is a system used by banks to manage risks related to currency exchange rate fluctuations. Exchange rate risk can arise in banking activities such as the sale or purchase of foreign currency, or in investment banking activities abroad. To manage exchange rate risk, banks typically adopt a strategy that involves the use of financial instruments such as foreign exchange derivatives (such as forward contracts, futures, and options). The Exchange Rate Risk Internal

Control System also includes internal control processes to ensure that banks understand and control the risks associated with such activities, and that they comply with applicable regulations and industry standards. Some processes that may be related to the Exchange Rate Risk Internal Control System include: (1) Risk identification, namely banks must determine the type of exchange rate risk they face and understand how this risk can affect their financial position; (2) Risk evaluation, namely banks must evaluate the level of risk they face and determine whether the level of risk is acceptable or needs to be controlled; (3) Strategy development, namely banks must develop strategies to manage the exchange rate risks they face, for example by adopting a non-exposure net position or by using financial instruments such as foreign exchange derivatives; (4) Implementation, namely banks must ensure that the strategies developed are implemented effectively and that exchange rate risks are controlled; (5) Monitoring and revision, namely banks must monitor the results of the strategies implemented and make revisions if necessary to ensure that exchange rate risk is controlled.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Exchange Rate Risk Measurement

There are several methods for measuring Exchange Rate Risk, including:

First, Value-at-Risk (VaR), which is the method used to measure exchange rate risk. This method helps determine the maximum amount of loss that may occur on a particular currency position within a certain time period and confidence level. The following are the stages in measuring exchange rate risk using VaR:

- (1) Determine the analysis time period, namely VaR can be applied for daily, weekly or monthly time periods.
- (2) Determine the level of confidence, namely the level of confidence is the level of probability in percentage, for example 1%, 5%, or 10%. The confidence level determines the maximum amount of loss that may occur.
- (3) Determine the return distribution, that is, returns from currency positions can be compared with a normal distribution or other more suitable distribution.
- (4) Calculate VaR, that is, after the return distribution is determined, VaR can be found by looking for a value at a certain level of confidence in the return distribution. This is the maximum possible loss amount on a currency position.
- (5) VaR validation, namely after the VaR is found, validation can be carried out by backtesting to ensure that the estimated VaR truly represents the existing risk.

VaR is a useful tool in measuring exchange rate risk, but it must be used carefully and in the right context. This method has several limitations, such as assumptions about return distribution and a limited analysis period. Therefore, it is important to properly understand the methodology and interpretation of VaR before using it.

Second, Stress Testing, which is a method for measuring exchange rate risk by taking into account bad scenarios in the economy or currency market. This method allows companies or investors to understand how exchange rates will affect their finances in extreme situations and makes them better prepared to deal with such risks. In stress testing exchange rate risk, analysts take into account several scenarios such as: (1) Sharp depreciation of the national currency; (2) Unexpected increases in interest rates; (3) Political changes affecting currency markets; and (4) Global economic crisis. Once these scenarios are applied to a company's financial projections or an investor's portfolio, they can see how changes in exchange rates will affect their finances and take action to address existing risks.

Third, Scenario Analysis, which is the method used to measure exchange rate risk. This method involves the identification and evaluation of various potential scenarios that may occur on the level of currency exchange rates, and estimating the impact of these scenarios on the company's financial position. The steps in measuring exchange rate risk using the scenario analysis method are as follows: (1) Identification of exchange rate risk, namely that the company must first identify the existing exchange rate risk and determine the assets and liabilities that are exposed to that risk; (2) Identification of potential scenarios, namely after identifying risks, the company must determine potential scenarios that may occur at the level of currency exchange

rates, such as currency appreciation or depreciation; (3) Evaluate the impact of scenarios, namely the company must evaluate the impact of each potential scenario on the company's financial position, including revenue, profits, and assets and liabilities; (4) Determining mitigation actions, namely after evaluating the impact of the scenario, the company can determine mitigation actions to minimize exchange rate risk, such as hedging or changing the company's financial position; and (5) Monitoring and review, namely after measuring exchange rate risk and determining mitigation actions, the company must regularly monitor and review the exchange rate situation and make changes to actions if necessary.

Fourth, Sensitivity Analysis, which is the method used to measure exchange rate risk. This method helps companies identify how changes in exchange rate levels will affect their profits or losses. To carry out sensitivity analysis, a company must identify the variables that influence exchange rate risk, such as sales volume, product price and production costs. Then, the company creates a hypothesis about how changes in the exchange rate level will affect each of these variables. After that, companies use simulations to evaluate how changes in exchange rate levels will affect their profits or losses. This can be done by creating several different scenarios, such as a particular currency appreciation or depreciation scenario. The results of sensitivity analysis can be used by companies to take action to reduce exchange rate risk, such as using hedging or improving their cash flow.

Fifth, Contract Forward Hedging, which is the method used to measure exchange rate risk. In this method, the company enters into a contract to buy and sell foreign currency in the future at a price that has been determined now. The aim is to protect the company's position against the risk of exchange rate fluctuations. The way this Contract Forward Hedging method works is as follows:

- (1) Risk Identification, namely that the company must determine the type of exchange rate risk that will be addressed and estimate the magnitude of the risk.
- (2) Determine the Forward Contract, namely the company determines the forward contract by estimating the amount of foreign currency that will be received or issued within a certain time period.
- (3) Hedging with a Forward Contract, namely the company buys or sells foreign currency at a predetermined price through a forward contract.
- (4) Contract Implementation, namely when executing the contract, the company will obtain protection against the risk of exchange rate fluctuations.

Contract Forward Hedging method can help companies limit losses due to exchange rate fluctuations. However, keep in mind that there are transaction fees that must be incurred to carry out this method. Therefore, companies must take these costs into account before entering into a forward contract.

Sixth, Monte Carlo Simulation, which is a method used to estimate exchange rate risk using random samples from the underlying probability distribution. In the context of measuring exchange rate risk, it can be used to estimate exchange rate fluctuations over a certain period of time. The steps in using the Monte Carlo Simulation method for measuring exchange rate risk include: (1) Identifying variables that influence the exchange rate, such as interest rates, inflation rates, and economic growth rates; (2) Estimated probability distributions for each variable, which may be based on historical data or expert opinion; (3) Generate random samples from the probability distribution for each variable and simulate how fluctuations in exchange rates would occur; (4) Repeat step 3 several times to generate many simulation samples and use the results to estimate the probability distribution of exchange rate fluctuations; and (5) Use the resulting probability distribution to determine the level of exchange rate risk, such as a certain standard deviation or percentile. Monte Carlo Simulation methods allow companies to better estimate exchange rate risks and make more informative decisions, such as deciding to hedge or take a position in a particular currency. However, this method is only an estimate and cannot provide definite results.

Mapping Literature Review around Problems in Exchange Rate Risk

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, exchange rate risk management on gold, namely the process of minimizing risks associated with changes in foreign currency exchange rates. Gold is an asset that is frequently traded and has a stable value, so many companies choose to buy gold as a hedge against exchange rate risk.

Second, exchange rate risk management in foreign currencies, namely the process of identifying, analyzing and minimizing the negative effects of changes in foreign currency exchange rates on business. This is especially important for companies that operate abroad or that carry out transactions in foreign currencies, as changes in exchange rates can affect the company's profitability and financial condition.

Third, the determinants of exchange rate risk, namely: Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Growth Opportunity, Hedging, dividend policy, company size.

Fourth, the influence of exchange rate risk on Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, stock returns,

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding exchange rate risks in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 1979 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 239 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding exchange rate risks in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 11 clusters and 118 items. Cluster 1 consists of 21 items, cluster 2 consists of 19 items, cluster 3 consists of 16 items, cluster 4 consists of 12 items, cluster 5 consists of 11 items, cluster 6 consists of 10 items, cluster 7 consists of 8 items, cluster 8 consists of 8 items, cluster 9 consists of 7 items, cluster 10 consists of 5 items, and cluster 11 consists of 1 item.
- Based on a literature review, there are 6 main research themes surrounding exchange rate risk in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) Definition and objectives of risk management; (2) Risk monitoring; (3) Strategy, risk level, policies, procedures, limits; (4) Identification, monitoring, control, information systems; (5) Risk measurement methods; and (6) Other issues related to risk.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

REFERENCES

[Sahni, S.](#) and [Singh Kaurav, R.P.](#) (2023), "What? Why? When? How? Where? of Technology-Based Bibliometric Review", [Rana, S.](#), [Singh, J.](#) and [Kathuria, S.](#) (Ed.) *Advancing Methodologies of Conducting Literature Review in Management Domain (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 2)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 79-101. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520230000002005>

[Anlesinya, A.](#) and [Dadzie, S.A.](#) (2023), "Technology and the Conduct of Bibliometric Literature Reviews in Management: The Software Tools, Benefits, and Challenges", [Rana, S.](#), [Singh, J.](#) and [Kathuria, S.](#) (Ed.) *Advancing Methodologies of Conducting Literature Review in Management Domain (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 2)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 57-78. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520230000002004>

- [Mulet-Forteza, C., Genovart-Balaguer, J. and Horrach-Rosselló, P.](#) (2022), "Bibliometric Studies in the Hospitality and Tourism Field: A Guide for Researchers", [Okumus, F., Rasoolimanesh, S.M. and Jahani, S.](#) (Ed.) *Contemporary Research Methods in Hospitality and Tourism*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 55-76. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80117-546-320221005>
- [Ülker, P., Ülker, M. and Karamustafa, K.](#) (2023), "Bibliometric analysis of bibliometric studies in the field of tourism and hospitality", *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 797-818. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-10-2021-0291>
- [Song, Y. and Cao, J.](#) (2022), "An ARIMA-based study of bibliometric index prediction", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 74 No. 1, pp. 94-109. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-03-2021-0072>
- [Akhil, M.P.](#) (2022), "Employing Bibliometric Analysis to Identify Emerging Technologies in the Insurance Industry", [Sood, K., Balusamy, B., Grima, S. and Marano, P.](#) (Ed.) *Big Data Analytics in the Insurance Market (Emerald Studies in Finance, Insurance, and Risk Management)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 207-220. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80262-637-720221011>
- [Ahuja, D., Bhardwaj, P. and Madan, P.](#) (2023), "Money Laundering: A Bibliometric Review of Three Decades from 1990 to 2021", [Tyagi, P., Grima, S., Sood, K., Balamurugan, B., Özen, E. and Eleftherios, T.](#) (Ed.) *Smart Analytics, Artificial Intelligence and Sustainable Performance Management in a Global Digitalised Economy (Contemporary Studies in Economic and Financial Analysis, Vol. 110B)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 55-72. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1569-37592023000110B003>
- [Güngör Göksu, G.](#) (2023), "A retrospective overview of the Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting and Financial Management using bibliometric analysis", *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, Vol. 35 No. 2, pp. 264-295. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBAFM-04-2022-0061>
- [Wani, J.A., Ganaie, S.A. and Rehman, I.U.](#) (2023), "Mapping research output on library and information science research domain in South Africa: a bibliometric visualisation", *Information Discovery and Delivery*, Vol. 51 No. 2, pp. 194-212. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-10-2021-0115>
- [Ralph, A. and Arora, A.](#) (2023), "A bibliometric study of reference literature on youth unemployment", *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, Vol. 17 No. 6, pp. 1338-1367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-04-2022-0062>
- [Ryan, J.C.](#) (2021), "Retaining, resigning and firing: bibliometrics as a people analytics tool for examining research performance outcomes and faculty turnover", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 50 No. 5, pp. 1316-1335. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-12-2019-0676>
- [Mokhtari, H., Barkhan, S., Haseli, D. and Saberi, M.K.](#) (2021), "A bibliometric analysis and visualization of the Journal of Documentation: 1945–2018", *Journal of Documentation*, Vol. 77 No. 1, pp. 69-92. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-08-2019-0165>
- [Farooq, R.](#) (2024), "A review of knowledge management research in the past three decades: a bibliometric analysis", *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, Vol. 54 No. 2, pp. 339-378. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJKMS-08-2021-0169>

- [Siddique, N.](#), [Ur Rehman, S.](#), [Ahmad, S.](#), [Abbas, A.](#) and [Khan, M.A.](#) (2023), "Library and information science research in the Arab World: a bibliometric analysis 1951–2021", *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, Vol. 72 No. 1/2, pp. 138-159. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-06-2021-0103>
- [Islam, M.A.](#) and [Widen, G.](#) (2023), "Bibliometric analysis of the VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems: 2000–2020", *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, Vol. 53 No. 3, pp. 467-490. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJKMS-07-2020-0126>
- [Perannagari, K.T.](#) and [Gupta, S.](#) (2022), "Mapping the Intellectual Structure of Artificial Neural Network Research in Business Domain: A Retrospective Overview Using Bibliometric Review", [Rana, S.](#), [Sakshi](#) and [Singh, J.](#) (Ed.) *Exploring the Latest Trends in Management Literature (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 1)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 35-59. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520220000001003>
- [Davidescu, A.A.](#), [Hapau, R.G.](#) and [Manta, E.M.](#) (2022), "Impact of Crises on Capital Market Volatility: A Bibliometric Analysis", [Grima, S.](#), [Özen, E.](#) and [Boz, H.](#) (Ed.) *The New Digital Era: Other Emerging Risks and Opportunities (Contemporary Studies in Economic and Financial Analysis, Vol. 109B)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 21-53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1569-37592022000109B003>
- [Ali, Q.](#), [Parveen, S.](#), [Aspiranti, T.](#), [Nurhayati, N.](#) and [Rusgianto, S.](#) (2023), "Barriers to the adoption of Islamic banking: a bibliometric analysis", *International Journal of Ethics and Systems*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOES-01-2023-0001>
- [Kumar, S.](#), [Goyal, P.](#), [Kumar, V.](#) and [Vandana.](#) (2022), "Cultural Diversity in Tourism: A Bibliometric Analysis of 33 Years (1988–2021)", [Rana, S.](#), [Sakshi](#) and [Singh, J.](#) (Ed.) *Exploring the Latest Trends in Management Literature (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 1)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 147-168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520220000001008>
- [Chhtrapati, D.](#), [Trivedi, D.](#), [Chaudhari, S.P.](#), [Sharma, A.](#) and [Bhatt, A.](#) (2024), "Global research performance on social media security: a bibliometric visualization analysis", *Information Discovery and Delivery*, Vol. 52 No. 1, pp. 101-113. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-04-2022-0029>